

UNIVERSIDADE PRESBITERIANA MACKENZIE

GUILHERME DANTAS SCRAMIM

**THE INCIDENT OF DISREGARD OF THE CORPORATE PERSONALITY IN SPECIAL
CIVIL COURTS: ADEQUACY AND LIMITS**

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Trabalho de Conclusão de Curso
apresentado como requisito para
obtenção do título de Bacharel no
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ORIENTADOR(A): PROFESSORA DOUTORA ALESSANDRA APARECIDA
CALVOSO GOMES PIGNATARI

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Aprovad(o)a em:

BANCA EXAMINADORA

Examinador(a): Prof. Doutora Alessandra Aparecida Calvoso Gomes Pignatari

Examinador(a): Prof. Doutora Bianca Mendes Pereira Richter

Examinador(a): Prof. Doutora Beatriz Valente Felitte

THE INCIDENT OF DISREGARD OF THE CORPORATE PERSONALITY IN SPECIAL CIVIL COURTS: ADEQUACY AND LIMITS

Guilherme Dantas Scramim

Resumo: Examina-se a admissibilidade e, sobretudo, a adequação procedimental do incidente de desconsideração da personalidade jurídica (IDPJ) no âmbito dos Juizados Especiais Cíveis (JEC). A pesquisa parte da tensão entre os princípios da Lei nº 9.099/1995 – simplicidade, celeridade e economia processual – e a complexidade potencial do IDPJ, conforme disciplinado pelo Código de Processo Civil de 2015. No plano do direito material, contrapõem-se a teoria maior (art. 50 do CC), que exige prova objetiva de abuso da personalidade, e a teoria menor (art. 28, § 5º, do CDC), que flexibiliza os requisitos em favor da tutela do consumidor. O estudo discute a extensão do IDPJ (art. 1.062 do CPC/2015) e propõe critérios de compatibilização com a Lei 9.099/1995: inclusão de sócios desde a petição inicial, contraditório nos próprios autos, uso preferencial da prova documental e migração de rito quando a instrução for complexa. Conclui-se pela compatibilidade do IDPJ aos Juizados Especiais Cíveis, condicionada a manejo parcimonioso e finalístico, preservando a vocação simplificada do microsistema.

Palavras chaves: Juizados Especiais Cíveis; incidente de desconsideração da personalidade jurídica; microsistema dos Juizados Especiais; contraditório substancial.

Abstract: This study examines the admissibility and, above all, the procedural adequacy of the incident of disregard of legal personality (IDPJ) within the scope of the Small Claims Courts (Juizados Especiais Cíveis – JEC). The research stems from the tension between the principles established by Law No. 9,099/1995—simplicity, promptness, and procedural economy—and the potential complexity of the IDPJ as regulated by the Code of Civil Procedure of 2015. From the perspective of substantive law, the analysis contrasts the major theory (Article 50 of the Civil Code), which requires objective proof of abuse of legal personality, with the minor theory (Article 28, § 5, of the Consumer Protection Code), which relaxes the requirements in favor of consumer protection. The study discusses the scope of the IDPJ (Article 1,062 of the CPC/2015) and proposes criteria for harmonization with Law 9,099/1995: inclusion of partners from the initial petition, adversarial proceedings within the same case record, preferential use of documentary evidence, and procedural migration when the evidentiary phase proves complex. It concludes that the IDPJ is

compatible with the Small Claims Courts, provided it is applied with restraint and in accordance with its purpose, thereby preserving the simplified nature of the microsystem.

Key words: Small Claims Courts; Incident of Disregard of Legal Personality; Microsystem of the Special Civil Courts; Substantive Right to Be Heard.

Sumário: 1. Introduction. 2. The Disregard of the Corporate Entity in Brazilian Law 2.1 Origin and evolution of the doctrine. 2.2 Legal framework: Civil Code, Consumer Defense Code, and special legislation. 2.3 The incident of disregard of the corporate personality in the CPC/2015. 2.4 Direct and reverse disregard. 2.5 Major theory and minor theory. 3. Special Civil Courts and their Procedural Dynamics 3.1 Purpose, principles, and procedural rationality of Law No. 9,099/1995. 3.2 Jurisdiction and material limits. 4. The Application of the IDPJ in Special Civil Courts. 4.1. Statutory provision: extension of the incident through art. 1,062 of the CPC/2015. 4.2. Compatibility between the incident and the principles of Law No. 9,099/1995. 4.3. Practical difficulties: expediency versus procedural formalism. 4.4. The role of the right to be heard and the right to a full defense in the context of Special Courts. 5. Conclusion. References.

1. Introduction

Legal personality constitutes one of the pillars of contemporary private law by enabling the separation between the assets of the legal entity and the individual assets of its partners or managers. This asset autonomy provides security and predictability to economic and contractual relations, allowing for the organization of business activities with risk distribution. However, such a prerogative is not absolute: the legal system provides for exceptional mechanisms to overcome this protective barrier.

In this context, the disregard of the corporate personality has become consolidated in Brazilian law as an exceptional technique intended to curb the abusive use of asset autonomy and to preserve good faith in legal relations.

On the substantive level, the Civil Code conditions the episodic lifting of the corporate "veil" to the demonstration of abuse of personality, evidenced by a deviation of purpose or commingling of assets (Art. 50). Conversely, the Consumer Defense Code, within a protective framework, admits under Art. 28, § 5 a more flexible solution whenever personification

becomes a barrier to restitution, allowing the judge to reach partners or managers when necessary for fulfillment: "whenever its personality is, in any way, an obstacle to the reimbursement of damages" (BRAZIL, 2002; BRAZIL, 1990).

On the procedural level, the CPC/2015 provided specific treatment for the Incident of Disregard of the Corporate Personality (IDPJ), aiming to ensure the right to be heard and the right to a full defense (*adversarial principle*) before the attachment of the partners' assets. Governed by Articles 133 to 137 of the CPC, the IDPJ is considered an autonomous and formalized institute, applicable at all stages of the process (whether in the knowledge phase, enforcement of judgment, or execution based on an extrajudicial title), and may be initiated at the request of the party or the Public Prosecutor's Office, when applicable (BRAZIL, 2015).

Furthermore, Art. 1,062 of the CPC extends this regime to processes within the jurisdiction of the Special Civil Courts (JEC). However, this normative extension has raised controversies, since the procedural model of the IDPJ, with a specific adversarial stage and the possibility of staying the proceedings, appears to collide with the summary nature of the Special Courts and their structuring principles provided for in Law No. 9,099/1995: oral communication, simplicity, informality, procedural economy, and expediency (BRAZIL, 1995).

Thus, the central question of this work arises: to what extent can the Incident of Disregard of the Corporate Personality be applied in the Special Civil Courts' rite without compromising expediency, procedural economy, and other structuring principles?

Based on this problem-question, the present study starts from the hypothesis that the incident of disregard of the corporate personality is applicable to the JEC, provided that procedural adaptations are observed to preserve the speed and simplicity of the rite, without setting aside the constitutional guarantees of the right to be heard and the right to a full defense.

The general objective of this study is to propose criteria for the procedural compatibility of the IDPJ with Law No. 9,099/1995; as specific objectives, it seeks to: (i) clarify the dialogue between the major theory (Civil Code) and the minor theory (Consumer Defense Code); (ii) outline the method for forming an adversarial process suitable for the summary rite; and (iii) systematize reflections on the adequacy of the IDPJ from the perspective of appellate impacts and costs (attorney fees) within the Special Courts environment.

Methodologically, the work adopts a qualitative and deductive approach, based on a literature review and jurisprudential analysis, with emphasis on reference authors in procedural matters and recent decisions, mainly from Superior Courts. Also by methodological choice, the

present study adopts Articles 50 of the CC/2002 and 28 of the CDC/1990 as its main analytical axes, as they represent the dogmatic core of the theme all without neglecting special statutes that also contemplate hypotheses for overcoming the corporate veil such as Law No. 9,605/1998 (Environmental Law) and Law No. 12,846/2013 (Anti-Corruption Law) mentioned when relevant to the object of this article.

Furthermore, the research is situated within the scope of the so-called "microsystem" of Special Courts, an expression used by doctrine and jurisprudence to designate the set of summarized (simplified) and related rites, comprising the Special Civil Courts (Law No. 9,099/1995), the Federal Special Courts (Law No. 10.259/2001), and the Special Courts of Public Treasury (Law No. 12,153/2009). These statutes compose an integrated normative system, guided by a common matrix of principles, even though they present variations regarding material jurisdiction and the value of the claim (CASTRO, 2018).

The study is justified by the practical importance of the topic, given the demands in the Special Courts involving business corporations and micro-enterprises, and by its theoretical relevance, since the subject requires the reconciliation between procedural effectiveness and constitutional guarantees.

The research seeks, therefore, to analyze the limits and possibilities of applying to the IDPJ in the microsystem of Special Courts, examining, primarily, the dialogue between the rules of the Code of Civil Procedure and Law No. 9,099/1995, as well as the related jurisprudence. Finally, it intends to demonstrate that the procedural adaptation of the IDPJ, without the need to initiate an autonomous process, can reconcile the values of effectiveness and procedural expediency with legal certainty and respect for constitutional guarantees, ensuring the fair application of the disregard of the corporate personality within the scope of the Special Civil Courts.

2. The Disregard of the Corporate Entity in Brazilian Law

2.1. Origin and evolution of the doctrine

The disregard of the corporate personality did not emerge as a negation of the legal entity, but as an exceptional response to the misused application of asset autonomy. Personification fulfills a legitimate economic-organizational function: it separates assets, enables investments, and distributes risks; however, the corporate "veil" has also been

historically instrumentalized for creditor fraud, deviation of purpose, and the concealment of assets. In such cases, the episodic lifting of the personality does not annul the legal entity; it merely prevents abuse, reaching those who improperly benefited from it.

In a comparative perspective, doctrine identifies the theoretical matrix of the relativization of personality—when converted into an instrument of fraud—in the North American experience (the *disregard doctrine*) and in German legal constructs (concerning the abuse of corporate law). In Brazil, its reception initially occurred through jurisprudential and doctrinal elaboration throughout the second half of the 20th century, especially in corporate litigation and frustrated executions, establishing the maxim of prudence: asset autonomy is the rule; its overcoming is the exception (CHINI; HARTMANN, 2017).

Positive law was established progressively. The Consumer Defense Code (1990) anticipated hypotheses for overcoming the veil, including reaching partners or managers when abuse is present, by providing that the legal personality may be disregarded "whenever its personality is, in any way, an obstacle to the reimbursement of damages" (Art. 28, § 5) (BRAZIL, 1990). The Civil Code (2002) systematized the theme in a more restrictive manner, conditioning the disregard to the demonstration of abuse of personality (Art. 50), evidenced by a deviation of purpose or commingling of assets; later, Law No. 13,874/2019 (known as the "Economic Freedom Law") densified these concepts, providing greater objectivity and curbing automatic applications.

In this way, the legislation authorizes the disregard of the personality upon demonstrating: (i) deviation of purpose (a willful act to defraud/harm creditors) or (ii) commingling of assets (an objective "mixing" of assets). Law 13,874/2019 sought to curb this shortcut by typifying these concepts in Art. 50 of the Civil Code and requiring concrete evidence (e.g., cross-payments, transfers without consideration, use of the corporation as an "asset projection" of the partner), moving away from decisions based on generic presumption (BRAZIL, 2002; BRAZIL, 2019).

The next step was procedural. The CPC/2015 organized the matter as an incident equipped with a specific adversarial stage and applicability in all phases (Arts. 133–137), reducing the margin of surprise and imposing minimum guarantees on those affected. Furthermore, Art. 1,062 extended this regime to the microsystem of Special Civil Courts, conditioning its application to compatibility with the principles of Law No. 9,099/1995 (oral communication, simplicity, informality, economy, and expediency) (BRAZIL, 2015; BRAZIL, 1995). Specific literature on Special Courts records this shift: with the CPC/2015, a procedural

model to be observed was consolidated without denaturing the summary nature of the rite (CHINI; HARTMANN, 2017).

Finally, the legislative trajectory reveals an arc of expansion: from the civil-consumerist core to sectorial areas (for example, in the environmental and anti-corruption fields), where disregard also serves the protection of public interest.

This briefly outlined historical-normative path, as well as the legislative approach that will be carried out in the following item (without any exhaustive claim, due to the limits and scopes of this research), prepares the reasoning for the central debate of this work: how to reconcile a potentially complex instrument with the summary rite of the Special Courts, preserving the adversarial principle and effectiveness without creating a "process within a process"?

2.2. Legal framework: Civil Code, Consumer Defense Code, and special legislation

The legal regime for the disregard of the corporate personality in Brazil rests on two main normative axes: the Civil Code and the Consumer Defense Code, supplemented by sectorial statutes. In the Civil Code, Art. 50 conditions the episodic lifting of the corporate "veil" to the demonstration of abuse of personality, evidenced by a deviation of purpose or commingling of assets. Law No. 13,874/2019 (Economic Freedom Law) densified these concepts, providing greater objectivity and reinforcing the exceptional nature of the measure to discourage its automatic application. In summary, substantive law (of a civil matrix) requires concrete evidence of abuse and links the extension of liability to those who effectively benefited from deviation.

In consumer law, Art. 28 of the CDC allows for the overcoming of the veil when the corporate form obstructs reparation. The Superior Court of Justice (STJ) consolidated the interpretation of § 5 as autonomous from the *caput* (main provision), stating that the judge may disregard the legal entity "when its personality constitutes an obstacle to the reimbursement of injured consumers," even if all the hypotheses of the *caput* are not proven in the specific case (REsp 279,273/SP).

Parallel to this line of reasoning, the aforementioned Superior Court has also delimited who can be reached: the so-called "minor theory" (to be addressed in subsequent items of this research) does not, by itself, authorize holding a non-partner manager liable; in such cases, the regime of the so-called "major theory" (which enshrines objective abuse) is required, as

reiterated by the STJ (2021). In practical terms, jurisprudence applies Art. 28, § 5 of the CDC when there is an objective demonstration that the legal entity was used as a barrier to debt satisfaction (e.g., lack of seizable assets or corporate interposition), while maintaining a minimum standard of proof to avoid decisions based on generic presumption.

Finally, the Brazilian positive system includes special legislation that authorizes disregard in specific contexts, such as environmental law (Law No. 9,605/1998, Art. 4) and liability for corruption (Law No. 12,846/2013, Art. 14), among others. In these legal frameworks, the disregard technique does not operate solely in favor of private interests; it also functions as an instrument for the protection of public interests, reaffirming that the legal personality is a legitimate means of economic organization, but not a shield for the practice of illicit acts.

2.3. The incident of disregard of the corporate personality in the CPC/2015

Although the disregard of personality has been applied for decades in Brazil, there were no express and specific procedural rules to guarantee its implementation, leading to disparate doctrinal and jurisprudential understandings (VIEIRA, 2017, p. 57).

In this context, it was the 2015 Code of Civil Procedure that systematically began to codify procedural rules for the implementation of the measure (Articles 133 to 137), providing predictability and legal certainty to the parties (HIBNER; SILVESTRE, 2019). Indeed, this procedural statute inserted the institute as a type of third-party intervention—after all, a subject foreign to the procedural relationship (the person to be held liable) may enter a pending lawsuit, becoming a party (MARINONI; SILVA, 2015, p. 454).

Nonetheless, the IDPJ is distinguished from other typical third-party interventions (provided for in Art. 119 et seq. of the CPC), as its purpose is not to subjectively expand the scope of the claim for its own legal interest, but to allow the exercise of defense by those who will be reached by the asset-related decision. It is, therefore, an incidental third-party intervention, whose object is delimited and of restricted cognition (CHINI; HARTMANN, 2017).

Despite the nomenclature employed by the CPC/2015 (“incident”), its legal nature is a subject of debate. On one hand, some categorize it as a typical procedural incident, as it is an accessory matter involving resolution prior to the final decision of the main case, transacting through specific procedural acts and with its own procedural structure. On the other hand, some

authors argue that it is a true incidental claim, since the request for disregard inaugurates a new legal relationship between the applicant and the affected subject, with sufficient autonomy to justify the application of the principles of causation and defeat (*sucumbência*). Along these lines, it is argued that the decision resolving the IDPJ must impose the payment of attorney fees and corresponding procedural expenses on the losing party (HIBNER; SILVESTRE, 2019, p. 84).

The deepening of these theoretical divergences exceeds the limits of this study. However, it is undeniable that relevant practical implications arise from them—such as the need to set prevailing party fees in the decision that resolves the incidental topic that will be revisited in its own section, further on, with an approach related to Special Courts.

Without prejudice to the above, and more precisely regarding the procedural peculiarities of the IDPJ, Art. 133 of the CPC sets the "trigger" for the institution of the institute: "it shall be initiated at the request of the party or the Public Prosecutor's Office" (when its intervention is appropriate), shifting the matter from intuitive decisions to a rite with a minimum guarantee of defense for the affected party.

Regarding the timing and method of filing, Art. 134 allows the incident "in all phases of the knowledge process, in the enforcement of judgment, and in execution based on an extrajudicial executive title"; if the request is made in the initial petition, "the initiation of the incident is dispensed with" (the person to be affected is summoned immediately, without the need to stay the proceedings), whereas, if requested subsequently, "the initiation of the incident shall suspend the process." These commands outline the preferred option to resolve the controversy within the process itself, with suspension of the case only when strictly necessary to enable the adversarial process.

The specific adversarial stage is structured in three steps: (i) demonstration of the legal requirements for disregard (the request must objectively indicate elements of abuse, under the terms of substantive law [CC/2002, Art. 50, or CDC, Art. 28]); (ii) service of process (*citação*) of the partner, manager, or the legal entity itself "to manifest and request the appropriate evidence within a period of 15 (fifteen) days" (Art. 135); and (iii) minimum evidentiary stage, followed by a decision. Once the evidentiary phase is concluded (if necessary), Art. 136 determines that the incident "shall be resolved by an interlocutory decision," which preserves the progress of the main case and allows for adequate challenge by interlocutory appeal (*agravo de instrumento*) (CPC, Art. 1015, IV).

It is also worth noting that if the IDPJ is resolved by a final judgment (*sentença*), as

occurs, for example, when the request for disregard is made in the initial petition, the appropriate remedy will be an appeal (*apelação*) (Art. 1,009, § 3 of the CPC). In this sense, moreover, is the command of Statement 390 of the V Permanent Forum of Civil Proceduralists: “If the disregard of the corporate personality is resolved in the judgment, an appeal shall lie.”

Furthermore, it should be noted that doctrine and jurisprudence allow the initiation of the IDPJ in the second instance, by interpretation of Articles 134, 136, and 932, VI of the CPC, interpreted to mean that the incident may be presented in the second degree of jurisdiction only in cases of original jurisdiction of the courts, which are expressly provided for by the Federal Constitution. In these cases, as the decision on the IDPJ would be monocratic, the appropriate remedy is the internal interlocutory appeal (*agravo interno*), under the terms of Art. 136 of the CPC (ALMEIDA; VAUGH, 2018, p. 156).

Regarding the effects that may arise from the outcome of the incident, Art. 137 of the CPC links the IDPJ to the discipline of fraud against execution: if the request is granted, the alienation or encumbrance of assets made in fraud shall be ineffective in relation to the applicant; the delimitation of fraud shall observe the general regime of the CPC (Art. 792).

Indeed, the legislative option adopted in the CPC/15 highlights that the incident under study is not a mere execution expedient, but an institute with an incidental decision on the merits and relevant asset reflections, which is why jurisprudence and doctrine have repudiated the automatic use of the instrument and insisted on evidentiary parsimony as well as the objectivity of the grounds (CHINI; HARTMANN, 2017).

In short, the IDPJ—of the CPC/2015—provides procedural security to disregard: it establishes who can request, when to request, how to contest, and how to decide, in addition to projecting effects on acts of asset disposal. This legal model, as will be seen later (item 3 of this study), is applicable to the JEC (Art. 1,062), but requires calibration so as not to sacrifice the principles of Law 9,099/1995, avoiding the creation of an incident with unnecessary procedural chaining.

2.4. Direct and reverse disregard

The so-called “direct” (or “traditional”) disregard consists of the episodic lifting of the legal entity's asset autonomy to reach partners or managers when an abuse of personality is demonstrated evidenced, under substantive law, by a deviation of purpose or commingling of assets (Art. 50 of the CC). The central point is not to punish mere corporate default, but to curb

the improper use of legal personality as an instrument for illicit practices. The measure, therefore, is exceptional and purposive: it is limited to those who effectively benefited from the abuse and to the extent necessary to redress the damage, preserving the rule of asset separation.

Conversely, the so-called “reverse” disregard operates in a symmetrical situation: when the individual debtor instrumentalizes the corporation to hide assets or frustrate creditors, allowing the legal entity's assets to be held liable for the obligations of the abusive partner. The CPC/2015 expressly codified this modality by providing that the incident's regime also applies to the “reverse disregard of the corporate personality” (Art. 133, § 2).

Furthermore, the jurisprudence of the STJ has consolidated the legitimacy of the reverse path as a technique for protection against asset fraud through corporate interposition, as exemplified by REsp 948,117/MS (STJ, 2009) a paradigmatic case that recognized the possibility of reaching the company's assets when it is used as a mere asset projection of the partner to harm third parties (ALMEIDA; VAUGHN, 2018). Additionally, Statement 283 of the IV Civil Law Conference of the CJF enshrines the institute.

In both hypotheses, direct or reverse, proof of abuse is a nuclear requirement: an objective demonstration of deviation of purpose or commingling of assets is required. The subjective scope of the decision must be restricted to the beneficiaries of the abuse, and the objective scope must maintain proportionality, avoiding the indiscriminate extension to third parties in good faith (REQUIÃO, 2002).

On the procedural level, the specific adversarial stage of the IDPJ (provided for in Arts. 133–137 of the CPC/2015) functions as a safeguard against “decision-making automatism,” allowing for a minimal and focused evidentiary stage. In other words: by requiring the objective demonstration of the legal requirements for direct or reverse disregard, the service of process to the affected subject, and the minimal instruction of the incident, the legislator sought to ensure that the overcoming of the legal entity's asset autonomy whether in direct or reverse form occurs with full observance of procedural guarantees. This procedural structure prevents disregard from being decreed prematurely or without an adequate evidentiary basis, preserving the system's rationality and preventing the proliferation of unnecessary or disproportionate procedural acts.

2.5. Major theory and minor theory

The disregard of the corporate personality, as a technique for overcoming the asset autonomy of the legal entity, is not limited to a single theoretical model (as briefly noted in

previous sections of this study). Throughout the doctrinal and jurisprudential development on the subject, two major interpretive branches have consolidated to guide the substantive application of the institute: the major theory and the minor theory (HIBNER; SILVESTRE, 2019). As will be demonstrated, the distinction between these theories organizes the substantive requirements for disregard and conditions its evidentiary burden.

Under the major theory, of civil law extraction, overcoming the corporate "veil" depends on concrete proof of abuse of personality, manifested in a deviation of purpose or commingling of assets (Art. 50 of the CC). This is an exceptional clause, which should not be confused with mere default or the debtor's simple insolvency.

In the minor theory, the focus shifts to reparatory effectiveness and the protection of the underprivileged (*hipossuficiente*). Art. 28, § 5 of the CDC authorizes disregard "whenever its personality is, in any way, an obstacle to the reimbursement of damages," which eases the classic requirements of abuse and admits the lifting of the veil when asset autonomy functions as a barrier to the satisfaction of consumer credit (BRAZIL, 1990). The jurisprudence of the STJ, in interpreting this provision, recognizes that in consumer relations, the measure may be facilitated compared to the common civil regime, without, however, dispensing with objective elements (for example, signs of irregular dissolution, interposition of persons, or the rendering of compliance unfeasible), under penalty of trivializing the institute (STJ, REsp 279,273/SP).

Based on this theoretical differentiation, a specific functionality is outlined for each model: the major theory acts as a general clause for asset liability, requiring robust and careful proof of the abuse of legal personality, while the minor theory offers a gateway for credit protection in consumer relations when the corporate structure is converted into a mechanism of non-reparation. In both cases, the application of disregard must observe criteria of subjective precision—limiting its effects to the actual beneficiaries of the abuse—and asset proportionality, so as to avoid excessive or undue liability.

In the Special Civil Courts, this distinction acquires special practical relevance, as the definition of the applicable legal regime (civil or consumerist) directly impacts the standard of proof and the procedural format compatible with the principles of Law No. 9,099/1995, as will be demonstrated in the following sections of this study.

3. Special Civil Courts and Their Procedural Dynamics

The purpose of this section is to analyze the application of the Incident of Disregard of

the Corporate Personality (IDPJ) within the Special Civil Courts, considering the procedural peculiarities that characterize this summary rite. Although the doctrinal and procedural discussions surrounding this topic exceed the scope of this work, the essential procedural aspects provided for in Law No. 9,099/1995 will be addressed to the extent that they contribute to the understanding of the research object and the clarification of the questions formulated herein.

3.1. Purpose, principles, and procedural rationality of Law No. 9,099/1995

Law No. 9,099/1995 materializes, at the infra-constitutional level, the directive of Art. 98, I, of the Federal Constitution, according to which it is necessary to create mechanisms aimed at expanding access to justice for causes of lesser complexity, with rapid response and reduced costs. Its teleological purpose is to simplify the path to effective jurisdictional protection, preventing form from stifling the law without, however, sacrificing the right to be heard and the right to a full defense.

Art. 2 of Law No. 9,099/1995 explicates the guiding principles of the procedure: “oral communication, simplicity, informality, procedural economy, and expediency” (BRAZIL, 1995). Indeed: a) oral communication privileges the concentrated formation of judicial conviction in hearings, encouraging self-composition; b) simplicity and informality remove useless rigidities; c) procedural economy requires that each act add concrete utility to the outcome.

More precisely, it is accurate to state that the principle of simplicity in Special Courts is materialized through a "lean" procedural design and by anti-formalist procedural acts or options. The hearing, for instance, is designed to concentrate conciliation, evidentiary instruction, and judgment, reducing intermediate acts and avoiding undue delays. Furthermore, the judgment without a report (“the judgment shall dispense with the report,” Art. 38) summarizes this logic of reducing useless formalities; in the same context, there is the possibility of pleading without an attorney in small-value claims; likewise, the prohibition of third-party intervention (Art. 10) prevents the hypertrophy of the litigious object—which would divert the process from its vocation (BRAZIL, 1995). Everything converges toward a flow of acts necessary and sufficient for the useful solution of the conflict.

Expediency, in turn, emerges both from the legal architecture of procedural acts and from the simplified appellate regime: interlocutory decisions, as a rule, do not allow for immediate challenge, their review being deferred to the "unnamed appeal" (*recurso inominado*)

against the final judgment (Arts. 41–42). Such a design maximizes the temporal yield of the process and discourages dilatory strategies.

Additionally, procedural economy functions as a principle of efficiency: each act must add concrete utility to the result, avoiding evidentiary duplication and autonomous incidents without proportional gain (BRAZIL, 1995).

It is also worth mentioning that the directive to decide based on criteria of justice and equity (provided for in Art. 6 of Law No. 9,099/95) grants the judge plasticity to shape the procedure to the specific case, provided that the core of due process of law is preserved.

All of this constitutes an institutional and procedural design that transforms time into a variable of justice without renouncing minimum guarantees of defense. This means that, in Special Courts, time is not merely a matter of logistics: it is a criterion of justice. The rite was designed to deliver protection within a useful timeframe (single hearing, few acts, deferred appeal), reducing formalisms that only delay the solution without suppressing guarantees: there is substantial adversarial process, the possibility of essential evidence, and a reasoned decision. The aim, therefore, is the balance between effective expediency and sufficient defense.

These mentioned principles and regulations function as vectors of compatibility when the summary rite encounters more complex procedural institutes (such as the IDPJ). While they reject formalisms that delay the useful outcome, they require an adequate adversarial stage and objective evidence before restricting legal spheres—a requirement directly relevant to the handling of the incident of disregard of the corporate personality.

In summary, Law No. 9,099/1995 establishes a purposive procedural model: fast, simple, and economical, yet controlled by guarantees, which conditions the reception of extraordinary techniques to a parsimonious use functional to the fair outcome (CHINI; HARTMANN, 2017). This arrangement, as will be seen below (section 4), conditions the incorporation of techniques from the CPC/2015.

3.2. Jurisdiction and material limits

The delimitation of the jurisdiction of the Special Civil Courts constitutes a natural development of the procedural rationality studied in the previous section. If the preceding item analyzed the *how* of the procedure (its principles and objectives), this section addresses the objective and material boundaries that define the field of incidence of Law No. 9,099/1995. Understanding these limits is essential for the debate proposed in this work, as they provide the

basis for evaluating to what extent the IDPJ can be reconciled with the summary rite without denaturing its simplified and expeditious vocation.

Indeed, the jurisdiction of the Special Civil Court is functionally established for "civil causes of lesser complexity," with a focus on access and rapid response (Law No. 9,099/1995, Art. 3, *caput*). Art. 3 lists four determining criteria for jurisdiction: (i) value of the claim up to 40 minimum wages; (ii) matters then enumerated in Art. 275, II, of the CPC/1973 (a historical reference now read as an indicator of low complexity); (iii) eviction actions for personal use; and (iv) possessory actions regarding real estate whose value does not exceed 40 minimum wages (BRAZIL, 1995). In addition to the knowledge phase, Art. 3, § 1, attributes to the JEC the execution of its own judgments and extrajudicial titles up to 40 minimum wages; § 3 of the same article specifies that the choice of this rite implies a waiver of the credit exceeding the legal limit, except for conciliation (BRAZIL, 1995).

The legislator also delimited the subject matter negatively: causes of an alimony, bankruptcy, fiscal nature, and those of interest to the Public Treasury are excluded from the JEC, as well as those related to workplace accidents, probate residues, and the status and capacity of persons, even if they have financial content (Art. 3, § 2) (BRAZIL, 1995). Such procedural provision preserves the summary vocation: structurally complex themes, with extensive evidentiary instruction or strong collective impact, are not compatible with the JEC rite. For this reason, even within the ceiling of 40 minimum wages, conflicts requiring extensive technical evidence or an evidentiary extension incompatible with the single hearing (provided for in Arts. 27 and 28 of Law 9,099/95) may justify referral to the common procedure.

Regarding technical representation, Art. 9 allows for the personal pleading of the plaintiff up to 20 minimum wages, with the option of assistance by an attorney; above this threshold, assistance becomes mandatory (BRAZIL, 1995). This directive reinforces the JEC's function as a "gateway," without suppressing the adversarial principle and the parity of arms—especially when the defendant is a legal entity. The venue rules (Art. 4) favor facilitation of access, allowing the filing in the defendant's domicile, the place of fulfillment of the obligation, or, in indemnity actions, the plaintiff's domicile or the place of the event (BRAZIL, 1995).

All these elements are articulated within the microsystem of special courts: federal matters of up to 60 minimum wages are shifted to the Federal Special Courts (JEF), with their own exclusions (writ of mandamus, expropriation, tax executions, among others) and absolute jurisdiction where a Court Unit is installed (Law No. 10,259/2001, Art. 3 and §§) (BRAZIL, 2001). Conversely, claims against the State/District/Municipal Public Treasury follow the rite

of the Special Courts of Public Treasury (JEFP), whose Art. 2 sets the jurisdiction for civil causes of interest to these entities, also with a specific ceiling and exclusions (Law No. 12,153/2009) (BRAZIL, 2009). In summary: the JEC does not adjudicate treasury cases (which go to the JEFP) nor typical federal matters (which go to the JEF), which avoids overlapping rites and reinforces the coherence of the microsystem.

From a teleological point of view, therefore, the material and objective limits of Law 9,099/95 operate as an adequacy filter: they preserve expediency and simplicity without sacrificing due process of law.

In the specific context of the IDPJ, it is argued here that the institute may be handled in the JEC (as expressly provided for in Art. 1,062 of the CPC/2015), provided that the instruction remains compatible with the rite provided for in the microsystem of Special Courts; if the evidence requires incompatible complexity (broad accounting expertise, for example), the adequate solution is to migrate procedures, rather than hypertrophy the summary procedure. This will be explained in greater detail later (especially from section 4 onwards).

4. The Application of the IDPJ in Special Civil Courts

4.1. Statutory provision: extension of the incident through Art. 1,062 of the CPC/2015

As previously asserted, the CPC/2015 codified the disregard as an autonomous incident with a specific adversarial stage (Arts. 133–137) and expressly extended this regime to the microsystem of Special Courts: “The incident of disregard of the corporate personality applies to proceedings within the jurisdiction of special courts” (Art. 1,062). This rule eliminates doubts regarding admissibility but does not clarify nor does it provide parameters or limits for the method of reconciling the IDPJ with Law No. 9,099/1995. For its part, as also noted in this study, Law No. 9,099/1995 mandates that proceedings in Special Courts observe “oral communication, simplicity, informality, procedural economy, and expediency” (Art. 2).

A joint reading of these statutes leads to an integration model: the IDPJ is applicable, but it must be handled “in the manner of the Special Courts” that is, with predominantly documentary evidence, an adversarial process within the same case files, and without unnecessary attachments or delays, reserving the stay of proceedings only when strictly indispensable for the defense.

In this same direction, FONAJE (National Forum of Special Courts) established a

filtering criterion for the CPC within the Special Courts system: “Considering the principle of specialty, the CPC/2015 shall only apply to the Special Courts System in cases of express and specific remission or in the event of compatibility with the criteria provided for in Art. 2 of Law No. 9,099/95” (Statement 161).

In practical terms, there is express permission from the CPC; the evaluation of the IDPJ's compatibility in the JECs means prioritizing: (i) the inclusion of the partner in the initial petition, when evidence exists, for a decision in the final judgment; (ii) when subsequent, establishing an adversarial stage within the same process with lean instruction; and (iii) migrating the rite when the cause reveals incompatible evidentiary complexity (extensive expertise, large production of witness testimony), instead of hypertrophying the summary procedure (which will be clarified and addressed in more detail in the next section).

This arrangement preserves the vocation of the microsystem and avoids transforming the IDPJ into a “process within a process.” In summary: Art. 1,062 authorizes it; Art. 2 of Law No. 9,099/1995 benchmarks it; and Statement 161 conditions the application of the CPC/2015 on compatibility with the vectors of oral communication, simplicity, economy, and expediency.

4.2. Compatibility between the incident and the principles of Law No. 9,099/1995

Indeed, the extension of the incident of disregard of the corporate personality (IDPJ) to the Special Courts (CPC/2015, Art. 1,062) does not eliminate the substantive and procedural filter inherent to Law No. 9,099/1995; the vectors of Art. 2 condition the manner of introducing, instructing, and deciding the request to lift the corporate veil. The point is not to deny the IDPJ, but to reconcile it with a summary procedure that transforms time and cost into variables of justice, without renouncing the right to be heard and the right to a full defense.

At the operational level, compatibility is verified when the IDPJ is handled in a way that does not create unnecessary or undue complexity within the procedural rite. If sufficient elements exist from the outset, the partners should preferably be included in the initial petition, allowing the matter to be addressed in the final judgment without staying the proceedings. If the need arises subsequently, the adversarial stage must occur within the case files themselves, with predominantly documentary and objective evidence, reserving more intensive evidentiary acts only when indispensable. Suspension measures must be exceptional, justified by a real risk of restriction of defense (*cerceamento de defesa*), and for the strictly necessary duration.

The design of the JEC reinforces this directive. As previously seen, the law dispenses

with the report in the judgment (Art. 38) and prohibits third-party intervention (Art. 10), signaling a restraint of formalism and subjective expansions that might distort the rite. Consequently, the application of the IDPJ without separate case files, with lean adversarial proceedings and objective reasoning (linked to the substantive criteria of Art. 50 of the CC and/or Art. 28 of the CDC), is the path most consistent with the summary model.

When the controversy requires incompatible evidentiary extension for example, extensive accounting expertise or voluminous witness testimony regarding complex commingling of assets the solution is not to hypertrophy the JEC, but rather to recognize the absence of "lesser complexity" and migrate the rite. In other words, the very legal notion of "civil causes of lesser complexity" functions as a material limit to the permanence of the IDPJ within the microsystem, preserving both expediency and decisional reliability.

Finally, the integration with the CPC/2015 must observe the specialty of the Special Courts system. The orientation consolidated by FONAJE is clear: the CPC/2015 applies to the Special Courts only when there is an express remission or compatibility with the criteria of Art. 2 of Law No. 9,099/1995. In this light, the IDPJ is applicable in the JEC (Art. 1,062 of the CPC/2015), provided it is processed with evidentiary parsimony, a swift decision, and a proportional adversarial stage, avoiding the transformation of the incident into an obstacle to the primary goal of the microsystem: delivering effective protection within a useful timeframe.

4.3. Practical difficulties: expediency versus procedural formalism

The main tension in applying the IDPJ to Special Courts arises from the clash between the expediency and simplicity of Law No. 9,099/1995 and the formalism that often accompanies the initiation of the incident.

A first difficulty is evidentiary. The IDPJ usually requires an objective demonstration of deviation of purpose or commingling of assets (Art. 50 of the CC) or, in consumer relations, that the personification obstructs reimbursement (Art. 28, § 5 of the CDC). However, the evidence must be compatible with the rite: primarily documentary (statements, contracts, invoices, corporate emails, corporate acts), avoiding broad expert testimonies that paralyze the proceedings. When the controversy depends on complex expertise (e.g., an extensive accounting audit to map multi-corporate commingling of assets), the adequate solution is not to overburden the Court, but to recognize the absence of lesser complexity and migrate the rite (BRAZIL, 1995).

The second difficulty lies in the formation of the adversarial stage. The CPC/2015 allows that, if the request for disregard is made in the initial petition, the formal initiation of the incident is dispensed with, and the person intended to be reached is summoned immediately; whereas, if requested subsequently, a specific adversarial stage is initiated (Arts. 134–135). In the Special Court, the management most consistent with the principles of Art. 2 is: (i) including the partner/manager in the initial petition, when there are indications, for a decision in the final judgment, and (ii) if subsequent, processing within the same case files, with a single deadline and lean evidentiary production. Suspension must be exceptional, for the strictly necessary time, and only when indispensable to avoid a restriction of the right to defense (BRAZIL, 2015).

Furthermore, an apparent collision arises with the prohibition of third-party intervention (Art. 10 of Law No. 9,099/1995). The IDPJ, however, does not convey a typical third-party intervention, but rather a subjective expansion of liability within the same substantive relationship, provided that the legal requirements and the specific adversarial stage are observed. Reconciliation requires the judge to avoid attachments or autonomous incidents that replicate acts (e.g., double instruction), preferring a decision within the case files themselves—a solution coherent with the rule that "the judgment shall dispense with the report" (Art. 38) and with the logic of maximum procedural yield (BRAZIL, 1995).

Finally, there are risks of trivializing the institute. In serial or mass litigation, the request for disregard is frequently used as an execution shortcut in the face of mere default, without a minimum evidentiary basis. This instrumental use contradicts the exceptional nature of the IDPJ and generates procedural costs incompatible with the microsystem. Good decision-making practices include: (a) requiring delimited petitions (objective facts, documents, chronology); (b) summarily dismissing generic requests; (c) prioritizing written adversarial proceedings and, only in cases of real necessity, a specific hearing; and (d) providing objective and concise reasoning, indicating why the existing evidence is sufficient or why the cause must leave the summary rite.

Regarding the appellate level, the design of the JEC also restricts dilatory formalisms: interlocutory decisions do not allow for immediate challenge, with review being deferred to the unnamed appeal (Arts. 41–42), which recommends fast and stable solutions within the trial court itself (BRAZIL, 1995). There is discussion of exceptional hypotheses for immediate challenge (interlocutory appeal, writ of mandamus), as these involve specific jurisprudential criteria rather than the daily mechanics of processing the incident.

Attorney Fees in the IDPJ of the JEC. The Special Court of the STJ established the

understanding that it is appropriate to set attorney fees when the request for disregard of the corporate personality is rejected, as it characterizes a specific defeat (*sucumbência*) in the incident (STJ, 2025a; STJ, 2025b). In Special Courts, however, the special discipline of Art. 55 of Law No. 9,099/1995 prevails, according to which the first-instance judgment shall not condemn the losing party to costs and fees, except in cases of bad-faith litigation (BRAZIL, 1995). Thus, in an IDPJ decided in the 1st instance of the JEC, the setting of fees is not the rule (it depends on bad faith); whereas in the appellate phase (unnamed appeal), the losing appellant may be condemned to fees, pursuant to Art. 55 itself and FONAJE guidance (BRAZIL, 1995; FONAJE, 2025). In summary: the STJ directive on defeat in the incident applies but is subordinated to the special regime of the Special Courts (STJ, 2025a; STJ, 2025b; BRAZIL, 1995).

In short, practical difficulties do not suggest denying the IDPJ in Special Courts, but rather conditioning it to compatible management: documentary and objective evidence, proportional adversarial stage, preference for decision in the final judgment when inclusion occurs in the initial petition, processing within the same case files when subsequent, and migration of the rite whenever evidentiary complexity exceeds the summary vocation.

4.4. The role of the right to be heard and the right to a full defense in the context of Special Courts

Within the microsystem of Special Courts, the right to be heard (*contraditório*) and the right to a full defense (*ampla defesa*) are non-negotiable: they constitute a constitutional parameter that prevails even under a summary rite. The Constitution ensures "to litigants, in judicial or administrative proceedings, and to the accused in general, the right to be heard and the right to a full defense, with the means and remedies inherent thereto" (Art. 5, LV) (BRAZIL, 1988).

What Law No. 9,099/1995 does is model the provision of these guarantees guided by "oral communication, simplicity, informality, procedural economy, and expediency" (Art. 2) so that the exercise of defense does not turn into counterproductive formalism (BRAZIL, 1995). Thus, the defense is carried out with quality, but without erecting an apparatus of incidents that would denature the vocation of the procedure.

In the incident of disregard of the corporate personality (IDPJ), the CPC/2015 provides

a minimum architecture for defense. When the request is made in the initial petition, the formal initiation of the incident is dispensed with and the partner/manager is summoned immediately; when the request is subsequent, a specific adversarial stage is initiated, with the service of process to the affected party "to manifest and request the appropriate evidence within 15 (fifteen) days" (Arts. 134–135) (BRAZIL, 2015). Reconciliation with Law No. 9,099/1995 suggests that this adversarial process takes place within the case files themselves, with predominantly documentary evidence and objective reasoning regarding the substantive requirements (Art. 50 of the CC and/or Art. 28 of the CDC), reserving suspension only when strictly indispensable to avoid a restriction of the right to defense.

The directive of substantial adversarial process understood as the postulate requiring that parties have a real and effective influence on the formation of judicial decisions—also precludes surprise decisions. Indeed, the CPC/2015 requires that the party be heard before deciding on issues capable of affecting the outcome of the judgment (Arts. 9 and 10). In Special Courts, this means prioritizing clear and concentrated notifications, with a single deadline and an indication of the points of contention (e.g., signs of deviation of purpose or commanding of assets), avoiding successive notifications and duplicated acts. The right to be heard is, therefore, effective because it allows real influence on the judge's conviction and proportional because it does not create excessive formalism.

From an evidentiary perspective, the right to a full defense does not authorize an extension incompatible with the rite. Instruction must be calibrated to what is indispensable to verify the requirements for lifting the corporate veil. In practical terms, it involves minimum requirements for objectification (corporate documents, financial flows, acts of dissolution, accounting records) and the reasoned denial of generic evidentiary requests when the existing record is already sufficient for a decision a solution that preserves the defense without sacrificing expediency and procedural economy. However, when the defense demonstrates the need for extensive expertise or voluminous instruction, it is necessary to recognize the incompatibility with the JEC and migrate the rite, rather than hypertrophying the summary procedure.

In summary, the right to be heard and the right to a full defense structure the processing of the IDPJ in Special Courts: they inform the method of service, delimit the necessary evidence, and condition the reasoning; however, they do not authorize formalisms that annul the vectors of Art. 2 of Law No. 9,099/1995. The expected result is a real defense (and not merely ritualistic), provided with a parsimony of acts, capable of allowing adequate appellate

review.

5. Conclusion

The analysis developed herein demonstrated that the disregard of the corporate personality, although an exceptional technique for protection against the abuse of asset autonomy, is compatible with the microsystem of Special Civil Courts when handled with parsimony and guided by the vectors of Law No. 9,099/1995. The substantive axis Art. 50 of the CC (major theory) and Art. 28, § 5 of the CDC (minor theory) provides the normative substrate for the episodic lifting of the corporate "veil," while the CPC/2015 (Arts. 133–137 and 1,062) provides the minimum procedural architecture, the application of which, in Special Courts, depends on compatibility with oral communication, simplicity, informality, economy, and expediency. It is concluded that compatibility is not achieved by the mere literal transposition of the CPC, but by the functional reinterpretation of the incident considering the procedural rationality of the Special Courts.

Sections 3 and 4 of this research demonstrated that the summary rite of the Special Courts does not tolerate formalisms that compromise the expediency and effectiveness of jurisdictional protection.

Therefore, from a practical perspective, the study indicated operational criteria to prevent the IDPJ from creating an undue chain of procedural acts, the initiation of separate case files, or unnecessary suspensions: (i) a preference for including the subjects to be reached in the initial petition, when evidence exists, for resolution in the final judgment; (ii) when subsequent, processing the adversarial stage within the case files themselves, with predominantly documentary and objective evidence, limiting the stay of proceedings to what is strictly indispensable; (iii) dismissing generic requests, requiring minimum factual and documentary delimitation; and (iv) migrating the rite when the cause reveals evidentiary complexity incompatible with the summary procedure (e.g., extensive accounting expertise or voluminous witness testimony). These guidelines preserve the core of guarantees (right to be heard and full defense) without sacrificing the decisional efficiency inherent to the JEC.

In summary, the feasibility of the IDPJ in Special Civil Courts is not merely a matter of legal admissibility, but of procedural governance. When the judge handles the incident in a precise and restricted manner, with predominantly documentary evidence, an adversarial process within the case files, and objective reasoning anchored in Arts. 50 of the CC and 28 of the CDC, the

creation of a "process within a process" is avoided, and the summary vocation of Law 9,099/1995 is preserved.

The inclusion of the partner in the initial petition (when there are indications), the limitation of suspensions to the indispensable when the request is subsequent, and the migration of the rite in cases of incompatible evidentiary complexity constitute a set of best practices that balance effectiveness (repression of fraud and abuse) and useful time (reduced costs), legitimizing the responsible use of the IDPJ within the Special Courts microsystem.

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